

Review

Qigong for Managing Parkinson's Disease Symptoms: A Preliminary Review of Meta-Analyses.

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Abstract: Qigong, an ancient mind-body practice centred on movement and energy cultivation, offers a potential avenue for improving the quality of life, particularly for individuals with chronic conditions. This review focuses on meta-analyses regarding Parkinson's disease (PD), the second most prevalent neurodegenerative disorder, characterized by both motor (tremors, gait and speech impairments) and non-motor (depression, anxiety, sleep disturbances) symptoms. The objective is to assess the potential of Qigong to enhance various aspects of well-being in PD patients, including emotional state, balance, mobility, coordination, and tremor reduction. Furthermore, this review seeks to understand Qigong's impact on physical and emotional health, social engagement, and independence, and to evaluate its effectiveness as an adjunct or alternative treatment in early-stage PD. Findings suggest that Qigong holds promise in reducing anxiety and depression, fostering relaxation, and promoting overall physical and mental well-being by improving motor and non-motor symptoms of PD patients.

Despite promising results, methodological limitations include heterogeneous protocols, restricted populations, and scarcity of longitudinal studies, pointing to the need for more rigorous randomized clinical trials, with standardized protocols and diverse populations, to establish Qigong as a validated complementary therapy for PD.

Keywords: Parkinson's Disease; Qigong; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Quality of Life.

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1. Introduction

PD, also known as idiopathic degenerative disease, is a progressive neurological condition characterized by the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons, leading to a spectrum of motor, mental health, sleep, pain, and other health-related issues ^{1,2}. While there is no cure, therapies and medications can significantly alleviate symptoms. Common symptoms include tremors, painful muscle contractions (dystonia), speech difficulties, and olfactory and gustatory dysfunctions. PD results in high rates of disability and a substantial need for care ²⁻⁴.

The disease typically manifests in individuals over fifty, although younger individuals can also be affected. Men are statistically more likely to develop PD than women. A familial history of PD is also a significant risk factor. Exposure to air pollution, pesticides, and solvents may further increase the risk. Symptoms of PD worsen over time, leading to a progressive decline in physical and mental well-being, and consequently, a reduced quality of life ^{1,5,6}.

Figure 1: Parkinson's Disease: Key Signs and Symptoms

As well, non-motor symptoms such as cognitive impairment, mental health disorders (depression, anxiety), dementia, sleep disturbances, pain, and sensory disturbances. Dyskinesia and dystonia can further complicate speech and mobility ⁷⁻⁹.

PD is the second most prevalent progressive neurodegenerative disease worldwide in middle-aged individuals ^{1,10}. From 1990 to 2015, over six million people were affected, and projections suggest that this number could exceed twelve million by 2040 ¹¹.

Both motor and non-motor symptoms of PD significantly impact patients' lifestyles. The primary challenge is to minimize symptoms and slow disease progression. Pharmacological treatment is tailored based on cognitive status and functional deficits.

Levodopa or dopamine agonists are first-line treatments, but their efficacy diminishes as the disease progresses, leading to complications such as psychosis, compulsive behaviours, agitation, hallucinations, and depression, the most common comorbidity. Studies confirm that while these drugs alleviate some symptoms and delay progression, they do not prevent depression and anxiety ¹². Carbidopa is often combined with levodopa to reduce side effects. Anticholinergic medications, though less effective than levodopa, are associated with dry mouth, blurred vision, constipation, urinary retention, and in severe cases, memory impairment, depression, and anxiety. Monoamine oxidase B (MAO) inhibitors, such as selegiline, are also used but can cause delirium and hallucinations. Catechol-O-methyltransferase (COMT) inhibitors like tolcapone and entacapone are alternatives, but tolcapone carries a risk of severe liver dysfunction. Dopamine agonists, including bromocriptine, pergolide, and ropinirole, may be first-line treatments in younger patients (fewer motor fluctuations, longer life expectancy), with side effects including nausea, sedation, dizziness, and vivid dreams ¹³⁻¹⁵.

Overall, conventional pharmacological treatments for PD pose challenges due to their combination use, leading to significant and prevalent side effects. Therefore, individualized treatment and close patient monitoring are essential ¹⁶. Novel molecules are currently under clinical trial to address unmet needs, particularly in Parkinsonism associated with the GBA gene ^{17,18}.

Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) offers a holistic approach to managing various conditions, including PD. Practices like Tai Chi, Qigong, and Baduanjin aim to balance body and mind, regulate Qi (vital energy), and promote overall well-being ¹⁹. TCM focuses on restoring harmony within the body, mind, and spirit, treating the individual as a whole rather than isolated symptoms ^{20,21}.

Specifically, Qigong is recognized as a tool for chronic disease prevention and management, stress reduction, and physical and mental well-being promotion^{19,22}. It is accessible for patients with functional limitations, involving gentle, repetitive movements and controlled breathing to circulate energy and blood, balance organ function, mobilize muscles, strengthen joints and tendons, and enhance immune defences²³⁻²⁵. This practice naturally activates physiological and psychological self-repair and recovery mechanisms, focusing on posture, breathing, and mental concentration to promote longevity and quality of life^{19,26}.

This review of meta-analyses aims to evaluate the potential of Qigong in managing PD signs and symptoms, and its benefits in improving quality of life, emotional well-being, balance, mobility, coordination, and tremor reduction. It seeks to understand Qigong's impact on patients' quality of life, considering both physical and emotional aspects, as well as its ability to enhance social interaction and patient autonomy. Furthermore, it aims to evaluate Qigong's efficacy in combination with or as an alternative to conventional medical treatment in less severe cases.

2. Methods

2.1. Search strategy

To identify relevant systematic reviews and meta-analyses, researchers conducted a comprehensive search of four major databases (PubMed, Scopus, Science Direct, and Scielo) from their inception up to January 23, 2025. The search focused on Qigong as an intervention for PD, using a detailed formula: (Qigong OR Chikug OR "Qi Gong" OR "traditional Chinese exercises") AND (Parkinson OR Parkinson's OR Parkinsonism OR "paralysis agitans" OR "shaking palsy") AND ("Meta-analysis").

Titles and abstracts were screened by the researchers, with conflicts resolved through discussion. After the full-text search, the same method was used for the full-text assessment.

2.2. Eligibility criteria

This review included systematic reviews with meta-analyses of Qigong interventions in humans, published in English, Portuguese, Spanish, or French. Studies assessing PD motor and non-motor outcomes were included, while animal studies and non-Qigong interventions were excluded.

2.3. Data extraction

Data extraction was conducted by two researchers, with disagreements resolved through discussion with a third. For each included article, key information such as authorship, year, title, journal, number of included studies and their methodologies, and major findings were recorded.

3. Results

The flowchart (Figure 1) reports the selection of studies.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flowchart of Study Selection.

A total of 61 studies were identified. After duplicates were removed, 48 remained. After title/abstract screening, 16 studies were searched for retrieval. Two studies could not be found. Therefore 14 studies were included in the final analysis.

Table 1 summarizes the included studies.

Table 1. Major findings of the included studies.

Study	Studies assessed	Major findings
Song <i>et al.</i> ²⁷	15	Significant improvements were observed on most motor outcomes (UPDS III [ES=-0.444, p<.001], balance [ES=0.544, p<.001], TUG [ES=-0.341, p=.005], 6MWT [ES=-0.293, p=.06]), falls [ES=-.403, p=.004], and non-motor outcomes such as depression [ES=-0.457, p=.008] and QoL[ES=-0.393, p<.001]. Cognition did not show significant improvements [ES= -0.225, p=.477]).
Tan <i>et al.</i> ²⁸	18	Significant improvements in depression-related scales (standardized mean difference (SMD) = -1.30, 95% confidence interval (CI): -2.10 to -0.49, p = 0.002); Anxiety-related scales (SMD = -1.11, 95%CI: -2.14 to -0.08, p = 0.03), sleep disorder-related scales (SMD = -0.71, 95%CI: -0.99 to -0.43, p < 0.00001); Cognition-related scales (SMD = 0.91, 95%CI: 0.44 to 1.38, p = 0.0001); QoL also improved (SMD = -1.35, 95% CI: -2.38 to -0.31, p = 0.01; SMD = 0.99, 95% CI: 0.54 to 1.43, p < 0.0001).
Chen <i>et al.</i> ²⁹	7	Significantly positive effects on motor symptoms (SMD=0.59, 95% CI [0.24, 0.93]), walking ability (SMD=0.78, 95% CI [0.10, 1.47]), and balance (SMD=0.72, 95% CI [0.23, 1.20]) in patients with PD. Subgroup analysis showed Qigong exercise had a significant difference in improving motor symptoms and walking ability compared to passive control (P<0.01), and no significant difference compared to active control. Subgroup analysis of Qigong exercise revealed a significant difference in balance compared to both active and passive control (P<0.05).

McMahon <i>et al.</i> ³⁰	12	Nonpharmacological interventions demonstrated significant effects for Inspiratory Muscle Strenght (MD 19.68; CI 8.49, 30.87; z=3.45; p=0.0006; I2 =2%); Expiratory muscle strength (MD 18.97; CI 7.79, 30.14; z=3.33; p=0.0009; I2 =23%); Peak expiratory flow (MD 72.21; CI 31.19, 113.24; z=3.45; p=0.0006; I2 =0%); FVC (MD 0.30; CI -0.03, 0.63; z=1.76; p=0.08; I2=0%); FEV1 (MD 0.27; CI -0.02, 0.57; z=1.80; p=0.07; I2=0%).
Mustafaoglu <i>et al.</i> ³¹	60 (6 qigong)	Qigong (MD: 0.32; 95% CI (0.00, 0.64) was most effective in improving gait speed.
Yang <i>et al.</i> ³²	15 (Tai Chi and Qigong) (13 RCTs and 2 non-RCTs)	Tai Chi plus medication showed greater improvements in motor function (SMD, -0.57; 95%, CI -1.11 to -0.04), (BBS, SMD, -1.22; 95% CI -1.65 to -0.80), and time up and go test (SMD, -1.06; 95% CI -1.44 to -0.68). Compared with other therapy plus medication, Tai Chi plus medication also showed greater gains in motor function (SMD, -0.78; 95% CI -1.46 to -0.10), BBS (SMD, -0.99; 95% CI -1.44 to -0.54), and functional reach test (SMD, -0.77; 95% CI -1.51 to -0.03). However, Tai Chi plus medication did not show better improvements in gait or quality of life. There was not sufficient evidence to support or refute the effect of Qigong plus medication for PD.
Wang <i>et al.</i> ³³	40	Analysis of active and non-active comparisons showed significant effects for tai chi/Qigong (P<0.05) on global cognitive function, executive function, memory, visuospatial ability, and cognitive processing speed. Tai chi and Qigong can be beneficial for improving global cognitive function (SMD = 0.64, 95% CI: 0.39-0.90, I2 = 85%, P < 0.00001).
Jin <i>et al.</i> ²⁵	22	Mind-body exercises significantly improved motor function in PD patients, including UPDRS (SMD=-0.61, p < 0.001), TUG (SMD=-1.47, p < 0.001) and balance function (SMD=0.79, p < 0.001). Mind-body exercises also had significant effects on depression (SMD=-1.61, p= 0.002) and QoL (SMD= 0.66, p < 0.001).
Lai <i>et al.</i> ³⁴	10	Baduanjin significantly improved the motor function of patients with PD, based on the UPDRS Part III (MD -5.37, 95% CI -8.96 to -1.78, p=0.003) and Fugl- Meyer Assessment of Lower Extremity (MD 5.39, 95% CI 2.71 to 8.07, p<0.0001); It also significantly improved the balance of patients with PD, based on the BBS (MD 4.40, 95% CI 3.08 to 5.73, p<0.00001); As well, Baduanjin significantly improved the gait of patients with PD, based on the 6 min walk distance (MD 21.62, 95% CI 11.14 to 32.10, p<0.0001)
Tang <i>et al.</i> ³⁵	19 (7 taichi) (2 qigong)	Tai chi demonstrated significant improvements versus control for TUG and BBS.
He <i>et al.</i> ³⁶	58	Qigong was associated with improved outcomes in the TUG test (MD -5.54, 95%, CI -8.28 to -2.77)
Hao <i>et al.</i> ³⁷	60 studies Baduanjin Qigong training = 3 Taiji Qigong training = 8	Compared to a control, Taichi was able to show significant improvements in the UPDRS score [MD =-4.26, 95% CI = (-6.63,-1.88)] and the TUG test [MD =-1.56, 95% CI = (-2.59,-0.54)]. Baduanjin Qigong showed significant improvements against control in the BBS [MD = 5.51, 95% CI = (0.46, 10.55)].

Wang <i>et al.</i> ³⁸	62 Traditional Chinese Exercise (n = 5) including Qigong and Tai chi	Compared to occupational group activities, Tai chi and Qigong showed significant improvement effects on depression (SMD: -2.14; 95% CI:-4.10--0.18). Compared to stretching exercises Tai chi and Qigong showed significant improvement effects on depression (SMD:-1.58; 95% CI:-2.52--0.63).
Wu <i>et al.</i> ³⁹	15	The meta-analytic findings revealed significant improvements in balance outcomes [(BBS) (g = 0.83, 95% CI = 0.37–1.29, p= 0.000, I2 = 84%), TUG (g = -0.80, 95% CI= -1.13--0.47, p= 0.000, I2= 81%), and the one-legged blind balance test (g = 0.49, 95% CI = 0.13–0.86, p = 0.01, I2 = 10%)], as well as gait outcomes [gait velocity (g = 0.28, 95% CI = 0.02–0.54, p= 0.04, I2 = 64%), 6MWT (g= 0.32, 95% CI 0.01–0.62, p= 0.04, I2 = 15%), stride length (g= 0.25, 95% CI= 0.08–0.41, p= 0.003, I2 = 42%)], and motor symptoms [UPDRS part III (g= -0.77, 95% CI= -1.06--0.48, p= 0.000, I2 = 76%)]. However, cadence (g = -0.03) and step length (g = 0.02) did not differ significantly. The moderator shows that the effects of TCE on BBS and gait velocity were moderated by Pedro score, exercise type, control group type, and number of sessions. Meta-regression found that TCE (exercise duration, number of sessions, and session duration) was significantly associated with improved UPDRS-III and BBS scores.

UPDRS - Unified Parkinson's disease rating scale, TUG - Timed Up and Go Test, BBS - Berg Balance Scale, SMS - Standardized Mean Difference, CI - Confidence interval, TCE - Traditional Chinese Exercise, 6MWT - 6-min walking test, MD - Mean Deviation, QoL - Quality of Life, FEV1 - Forced Expiratory Volume, FVC - Forced vital capacity, ES - Effect size.

4. Discussion

The analyzed studies confirm Qigong's effectiveness in reducing motor symptoms associated with PD, demonstrating significant improvements in balance, mobility, and muscle rigidity. The study by Song *et al.* ²⁷ indicated a potential benefit of Qigong in enhancing motor performance, function, and quality of life. Furthermore, the studies by Chen *et al.* ²⁹ and Lai *et al.* ³⁴ suggest that Qigong and Baduanjin (an eight-exercise Qigong sequence) can contribute to increased motor function, walking ability, and balance in patients, with regular practice potentially reducing tremors and bradykinesia. Another interesting finding is the likelihood that Qigong exercises can enhance the effectiveness of medications like levodopa, potentially reducing adverse effects associated with long-term use, such as dyskinesias, as in the study by Yang *et al.* ³², in which Qigong was used as a complementary therapy alongside pharmacological treatments for PD.

Additionally, several studies highlight Qigong; some reviews indicate that techniques like dance or yoga may be equally effective in certain aspects, such as improving quality of life and balance. However, Qigong demonstrated superiority in improving motor functionality compared to passive therapies or inactive control groups. Consistent with prior findings Chen *et al.* ²⁹, demonstrated that Qigong had significant positive effects on motor symptoms, walking ability, and balance. For balance, Qigong also showed a significant improvement compared to both active and passive therapies. Furthermore, in the study by Yang *et al.* ³², Tai Chi and Qigong were used as complementary treatments to pharmacological treatment for mild to moderate PD. The combination of Qigong showed significant improvements when compared to pharmacological treatment applied in isolation.

For non-motor symptoms, Tan *et al.* ²⁸ and Jin *et al.* ²⁵ studies indicated that traditional Chinese medicine exercises might alleviate the severity of neuropsychiatric symptoms, including depression, anxiety, and sleep disorders, and improve cognitive function and overall quality of life in PD patients. These studies also suggest Qigong positively impacts mood and coping abilities, and its regular practice enhances sleep quality by reducing

insomnia and promoting deeper rest, consistent with earlier findings by Jin *et al.*²⁵. Consistent with prior findings Wang *et al.*³⁸, demonstrated that Qigong was an effective intervention for improving cognition in patients with PD, stroke, mild cognitive impairment, dementia, and traumatic brain injury; however, no RCTs were conducted for other neurological disorders. He *et al.*³⁶ conclude that mindfulness-based therapy, specifically Qigong, is a preferred non-pharmacological alternative based on motor/sensory intervention for patient rehabilitation.

Worthy of note, consistent with prior findings, He *et al.*³⁶, demonstrated that Qigong was performed two to five times weekly, leading to the belief that a higher treatment frequency would positively impact its effectiveness. According to Wu *et al.*³⁹, the frequency, number, and duration of traditional Chinese medicine exercises, such as Qigong, can affect the extent of their favourable therapeutic effects.

The observed benefits of Qigong can be attributed to various physiological and psychological mechanisms. This practice regulates the autonomic nervous system, balancing sympathetic and parasympathetic activities, which aids in stress relief and maintaining bodily equilibrium¹⁹. The repetitive exercises and mental focus characteristic of Qigong stimulate neuroplasticity^{40,41} promoting the formation of new neural connections. The activation of the body-mind axis, through a combination of gentle exercises, respiratory control, and concentration, significantly improves functional integration, culminating in rhythmic and controlled movements that enhance blood circulation and muscle oxygenation, contributing to recovery and overall well-being. In a simplified sense, Qigong practice can activate the parasympathetic response, promoting a reduction in heart rate, blood pressure, and cortisol levels, thus favouring a state of deep relaxation and reducing the impact of chronic stress^{22,26}. Consequently, it may be particularly effective in diminishing symptoms related to anxiety and depression^{40,41}. It is also suggested that Qigong can improve cardiovascular function by optimizing blood flow and tissue oxygenation, supporting recovery and alleviating physical tensions⁴²⁻⁴⁴. The practice also actively engages the vagus nerve, which plays a crucial role in modulating the central nervous system, assisting in stress reduction and fostering a state of deep relaxation⁴⁵. Controlled breathing, a core element of Qigong, facilitates a state of calm and internal balance^{46,47}. This respiratory practice contributes to improved physiological control over stress, enhancing the body's capacity to recover from stressful situations.

5. Limitations and Final Considerations

One of the main limitations in studies on the health benefits of Qigong, especially in patients with neurodegenerative diseases like PD, relates to the methodological variability among investigations. The heterogeneity in Qigong practice protocols, including differences in frequency, duration, and specific types of exercises performed, makes it difficult to compare results and can compromise the accuracy of the evidence obtained. Several studies adopt different approaches regarding the number of weekly sessions, the intensity of activities, and the duration of intervention programs, which makes it difficult to draw definitive conclusions about the consistent and comprehensive effects of Qigong practice. This lack of standardization in protocols is a challenge for the development of universal therapeutic recommendations.

It is noted that there is a scarcity of studies that include diverse populations, both in terms of geographical location and in the stages of PD progression. The majority of investigations focus on restricted groups, such as patients from a specific country or region, or in specific stages of the disease. This limitation reduces the generalizability of the results for different population groups and clinical conditions, as the response to Qigong may vary according to cultural and environmental factors and the stage of the disease. The inclusion of a broader and more diverse sample would allow for a more comprehensive understanding of the effects of the practice on different subgroups of patients.

Another important limitation concerns the scarcity of studies that assess the long-term effects of Qigong practice. Most available studies focus on short-term interventions, usually lasting a few weeks or months, leaving open the question of how the observed

benefits are sustained over time. As mentioned by Liu *et al.*⁴¹, the lack of data on the maintenance of the benefits of long-term Qigong practice represents a significant gap, and future studies should focus on this issue to validate the continued effectiveness of Qigong, especially for chronic diseases such as PD, which require long-lasting interventions.

Finally, it is essential to conduct rigorous, controlled, and randomized clinical trials that explore not only the motor benefits of Qigong but also more data on the effects on non-motor symptoms, such as depression and anxiety. The inclusion of adequate control groups and the standardization of Qigong protocols in future studies will contribute to a more solid and comprehensive understanding of the therapeutic potential of this practice in patients with PD. Only through methodologically rigorous studies will it be possible to establish Qigong as a widely recognized and validated therapeutic method for the complementary treatment of neurodegenerative diseases.

6. Conclusions

The analyzed studies suggest Qigong is a promising complementary therapy for PD, significantly improving motor symptoms like balance, mobility, and rigidity, potentially enhancing motor function and quality of life, and showing superiority over passive therapies. It may also complement medication. Furthermore, Qigong appears to alleviate non-motor symptoms such as depression, anxiety, and sleep disorders and may improve cognition. Proposed mechanisms involve nervous system regulation and neuroplasticity. However, methodological variability and limited long-term data necessitate further rigorous research with standardized protocols and diverse populations to solidify these findings and establish Qigong as a validated complementary treatment for PD.

With the growing interest in integrative therapies, Qigong may become a valuable addition to multidisciplinary PD care pending further validation.

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